

Solvent free accelerated synthesis of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole derivatives using microwave

M. B. Deshmukh*, (Miss) S. S. Jagtap and (Miss) S. A. Deshmukh

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : m_deshmukh1@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 23 December 2005, revised 25 May 2006, accepted 31 July 2006

Abstract : The expeditious solvent free synthesis of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole derivatives has been described. This involved the microwave exposure of reactants either in presence of catalyst or in absence of catalyst under solvent free conditions using easily available technique. The structures of the synthesized compounds were established on the basis of IR, PMR and elemental analysis.

Keywords : Heterocycles, benzothiazole, microwave synthesis.

Microwave irradiation has been used for variety of applications including synthetic organic chemistry¹. Benzothiazole derivatives have been studied extensively because of their broad spectrum of biological activities² and variety of industrial applications. Similarly pyrazoles show various biological and pharmacological activities such as anti-tumor and anti-inflammatory³ properties. Here, we report the synthesis of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole derivatives using domestic microwave oven, resulting in reduced time significantly. The classical approach⁴ for synthesis of these derivatives involves refluxing for several hours in presence of solvent, which result in generation of aqueous and organic waste.

Results and discussion

The reaction of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1) with acetylacetone afforded 2-benzothiazolyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazole (1a). A typical experimental procedure entails mixing of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole and acetylacetone in an open glass container without solvent and reaction mixture irradiated in a microwave oven for 1 min with intermittent irradiation to afford 1a in 90% yield. The formation of 1a has been ensured on the basis of its PMR. The singlets at δ 2.31 and 2.78 are due to two CH₃ and a singlet at δ 6.04 is due to CH supported the structure. Compound (1) on reaction with ethyl cyanoacetate under microwave irradiation afforded the compound (1b), 5-amino-1-benzothiazole-2-yl-1,2-dihydropyrazol-3-one (88% yield), in 2 min whose structure has been confirmed on the basis of IR and PMR. The IR spectra shows bands in the region 1650 and 3300 cm⁻¹

due to cyclic >C=O and NH₂ respectively. Further the compound was confirmed on the basis of PMR spectra. It shows singlet at δ 3.3 due to CH, singlet at δ 6.5 due to NH₂ and broad singlet at δ 12.3 due to NH proton. Compound (1) on reaction with phenylisothiocyanate afford *N*-phenylthiosemicarbazide-1,3-benzothiazole (1c) under a microwave irradiation within 30 s. which on reaction with ethyl chloroacetate and a catalytic amount of morpholine can be further elaborated to give compound 2-imino-3-(2-benzothiazolyl amino)-thiazolidine-4-one (1d). The conventional method requires refluxing for 6 h in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The IR spectra of compound (1d) revealed band at 1684 cm⁻¹ due to cyclic >C=O and 3152 due to NH and PMR spectra shows singlet at δ 4.083 due to COCH₂S and a broad singlet at δ 8.5 due to NH proton. Further compound (1) on reaction with diethyl malonate and ethylacetoacetate under microwave irradiation afforded 1-benzothiazole-2-yl-pyrazolidine-3,5-dione (1e) and 2-benzothiazol-2-yl-5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-pyrazole-3-one (1f) respectively. The IR spectra of 1e shows bands at 1646 and 1697 cm⁻¹ due to cyclic >C=O and the PMR spectra revealed singlet at δ 3.6 due to CH₂. The reaction of ethylacetoacetate can be carried out in presence of one or two drops of AcOH. The compound was confirmed on the basis of IR spectrum, which shows characteristic band at 1660 due to cyclic >C=O. Further PMR spectrum of 1f shows singlets at δ 2.3 and 2.7 due to CH₂ and CH₃ respectively. Reaction conditions, reaction time and yields of the synthesized compounds are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Yields and reaction conditions used for microwave assisted synthesis

Entry	Conditions	Microwave method		Conventional method	
		Reaction time	Yield (%)	Reaction time h	Yield (%)
1a	-	1 min	90	3	65
1b	-	2 min	88	4	80
1c	-	30 s	87	2	78
1d	Morpholine	3 min	82	6	75
1e	AcOH	2 min	84	5	65
1f	AcOH	3 min	89	5	78

Experimental

All m.p.s were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer (cm^{-1}) and PMR spectra (CDCl_3) on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (chemical shifts in δ ppm) using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of compounds in addition to the elemental analysis was checked by TLC using silica gel-G. All the compounds showed satisfactory microanalytical results for C, H and N. Microwave irradiation (MWI) was conducted in a Samsung M197DN (2450 MHz, 1500 W). All the reactions are carried out in an open glass container. The average bulk temperature at the end of reaction was measured by inserting a thermometer in the glass container.

2-Hydrazinobenzothiazole (1) : Compound 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1) was established on the basis of single crystal analysis⁵.

1-(2-Benzothiazolyl)-3,5-dimethyl-pyrazoles (1a) : A mixture of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1 mmol) and acetylacetone (1 mmol) was irradiated in MW for 1 min with intermittent irradiation at 130 °C. After completion of reaction, as determined by TLC examination, the crude product was recrystallised from ethanol. Yield (90%); m.p. 142 °C (lit. 140 °C); IR (KBr) 1620 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 2.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.78 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.04 (1H, s, CH), 7.0–7.5 (4H, m, ArH).

5-Amino-1-benzothiazole-2-yl-1,2-dihydro-pyrazol-3-one (1b) : A mixture of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1 mmol) and ethylcyanoacetate (1 mmol) was irradiated in MW for 2 min with intermittent irradiation for 1 min interval at 130 °C (monitored by TLC). The product was washed with water and recrystallised from methanol. Yield (88%); m.p. 130 °C; IR (KBr) 1650 (cyclic $>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 3300 (NH_2); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.3 (1H, s, CH), 6.5 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.0–7.5 (4H, m, ArH), 12.3 (1H, br s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O).

N-Phenyl thiosemicarbazide-1,3-benzothiazole (1c) : A mixture of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (0.1 mmol) and phenylisothiocyanate (0.1 mmol) was irradiated in MW for 30 s at 80 °C (monitored by TLC). The crude product

Scheme 1

was washed with water and recrystallised from benzene. Yield (87%); m.p. 142 °C; IR (KBr) 3120 (NH); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 6.5 (1H, s, NH), 7.2–7.4 (4H, m, ArH), 7.6–7.8 (5H, m, ArH), 10.5 (1H, br s, NH, exchangeable with D₂O).

2-Imino-3-(2-benzothiazolyl amino)-thiazolidine-4-one (1d) : (Conventional method) : To a mixture of **1c** (0.1 mmol) and ethylchloroacetate (2 ml) in ethanol, anhydrous sodium acetate was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 6 h, then cooled and recrystallised from methanol. Yield (75%). (Microwave method) : A mixture of **1c** (0.1 mmol) and ethylchloroacetate in presence of a catalytic amount of morpholine was irradiated in MW for 3 min with intermittent irradiation for 1 min interval at 130 °C (monitored by TLC). Then the product was cooled and poured onto ice-cold water and recrystallized from methanol. Yield (82%); m.p. 180 °C; IR (KBr) 1684 (C=O), 3152 (NH); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 4.083 (2H, s, COCH₂S), 7.2–7.37 (4H, m, ArH of benzothiazole), 7.65–7.75 (5H, m, ArH), 8.5 (1H, br s, NH, exchangeable with D₂O).

1-Benzothiazole-2-yl-pyrazolidine-3,5-dione (1e) : A mixture of **1** (0.1 mmol) and diethyl malonate was taken in an open container and one or two drops of acetic acid was added and further subjected to intermittent MW irradiation for 3 min at 130 °C and examined by TLC. The brown coloured oily mass obtained was crystallized from methanol to yield **1e**. Yield (84%); m.p. 145 °C; IR (KBr) 1646 (C=O), 1697 (>C=O), 3178 (NH); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.6 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.25–7.6 (4H, m, ArH).

2-Benzothiazol-2-yl-5-methyl-2,4-dihydro-pyrazole-3-one (1f) : A mixture of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (0.1 mol), ethylacetoacetate (0.1 mol), and a catalytic amount of AcOH was mixed thoroughly and irradiated in MW for 1 min with intermittent irradiation at 130 °C. The progress of reaction was determined by TLC and the crude product was recrystallized from methanol. Yield (89%); m.p. 110 °C; IR (KBr) 1610 (>C=N), 1660 (>C=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.7 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.0–7.5 (4H, m, ArH).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank NCL, Pune (India) and ICT, Hyderabad (India) for spectral analysis.

References

1. M. Larhed, C. Moberg and A. Hallberg, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2002, **35**, 717; C. Oliver Kappe, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. (Rev.)*, 2004, **43**, 6250.
2. Geoffrey Wells, Philip R. Lowe and Malcolm F. G. Stevens, *Arkivoc*, 2000, **1**, 779; Sushilkumar, S. Bahekar and Devanand B. Shinde, *J. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **47**, 237.
3. P. G. Baraldi, I. Beria, P. Cozzi, C. Geroni and A. Espinosa, *Bioorganic and Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 3911; Adnan A. Bekhit and Tarek Abdel Aziem, *Bioorganic and Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 1935.
4. V. I. Kelarev, K. I. Kobrakov and I. I. Rybina, *Chem. Hetero. Compd.*, 2003, 39; S. N. Sawhney, Pawan Kumar Sharma and (Miss) Asha Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 421; S. P. Singh, Subhash Sehgal, Lakhvinder Singh and S. N. Dhawan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, **26**, 154.
5. Rajnikant, Dinesh, Kamni, M. B. Deshmukh, S. S. Jagtap and S. R. Desai, *J. Chem. Cryst.*, 2005, **34**, 293.